

Perineal Injury Secondary to High-Pressure Water Jet: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anorectal trauma is an uncommon clinical entity that represents a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge due to the complex anatomy of the perineal region and the frequent involvement of adjacent pelvic structures. High-pressure water jet injuries, such as those associated with personal watercraft accidents, are a rare mechanism of trauma that can result in extensive disruption of the rectum, anal sphincter complex, and pelvic floor. The optimal management of these injuries remains controversial and should be individualized according to the extent of tissue damage and the patient's clinical condition.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 53-year-old female who sustained severe perineal trauma after falling from a jet ski and receiving a direct high-pressure water jet impact to the perineal region. Initial evaluation revealed extensive injuries involving the posterior rectal wall, anal sphincter complex, perineal body, and a vaginal laceration that had been primarily repaired at the site of the accident. Pelvic magnetic resonance imaging confirmed disruption of the elevator ani muscle and anal sphincters, as well as an approximately 10 cm rectosigmoid tear. The patient underwent surgical management consisting of extensive debridement and selective primary repair of the rectal wall and sphincter complex, followed by a laparoscopic diverting sigmoid colostomy. Postoperative recovery was favorable. Six months later, anorectal manometry demonstrated functional improvement after a structured pelvic floor rehabilitation program. Subsequently, laparoscopic colostomy closure with double stapled colorectal anastomosis was performed with an uneventful recovery. During follow-up, the patient achieved complete fecal continence with a Wexner score of 10.

Conclusion: Severe anorectal injuries caused by high pressure water jets are rare but potentially devastating. Early diagnosis, individualized surgical management, protective fecal diversion, and pelvic floor rehabilitation can lead to favorable functional outcomes, even in patients with extensive sphincter complex involvement.

KEYWORDS: Perineal Trauma, Anorectal Trauma, High Pressure Water Jet Injury, Diverting Colostomy, Pelvic Floor Rehabilitation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The management of rectal and anal trauma remains a topic of debate due to the lack of high-level evidence and the absence of a unified guideline to guide initial treatment (3)(8). This is because there is a risk that during initial management—such as diversion, drainage, or surgical washout—additional harm may be caused to the patient (4).

Penetrating trauma and destructive anorectal trauma represent a particular challenge for the colorectal surgeon, as these events are uncommon and the injuries encountered are usually secondary to lacerations from foreign bodies, with limited experience in managing severe anorectal trauma. The incidence reaches up to 3% in the population (7).

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Typically, patients with anorectal trauma are young and otherwise healthy individuals. When a force (air or water) is directed toward the perineum, it generally results in rectosigmoid perforation, since this is a spastic and angulated area (2).

For intraperitoneal injuries, primary repair or resection and anastomosis is always the best option, although it is essential to evaluate whether a diversion and delayed closure (followed by a damage-control laparotomy) should be performed. This group of patients is highly heterogeneous and has a very high rate of anastomotic leaks, particularly in those with comorbidities. For patients who cannot tolerate an anastomotic leak, a diverting colostomy is preferable.

For extraperitoneal injuries, various surgical groups and expert surgeons still recommend—in their papers and textbooks—rectal and anal surgical washout along with presacral space drainage, even though the latter has not been proven to provide actual benefits; it has only been described as a theoretical advantage.

Fecal diversion is appropriate for many patients with injuries involving multiple organs (5)(6), although it is not a strict rule, nor does it mean that all patients with rectal or anal trauma require or benefit from a colostomy. Assessment of injury severity, location, and non-operative management without colostomy is recommended in selected patients (9). When a diverting colostomy is decided upon, the best choice is a sigmoid colostomy performed laparoscopically.

A colostomy is considered indicated in intraperitoneal injuries, severe extraperitoneal injuries, and severe perineal lacerations (with or without pelvic fracture) (6)(10).

The treatment of extraperitoneal injuries depends on the degree of severity (1). Primary repair is rarely necessary, especially when the decision has been made to perform a diverting colostomy. This practice is usually difficult and incomplete and, in many cases, can even be counterproductive due to poor visualization of anatomical structures. These types of injuries are better left to heal by secondary intention, allowing communication between the presacral space and the rectal lumen (1).

Sphincter injuries require individualized and specialized management based on the approach and severity. Concomitant injuries to the vagina and genitourinary tract are common and must be evaluated and addressed during repair. When primary sphincter repair is chosen, it is important to expect only limited long-term success rates. If primary repair is inadequate or fails, reconstruction with a graciloplasty can be performed (3).

II. CASE REPORT

This is a 53-year-old female patient who was engaged in recreational activities. She suffered a fall from a personal watercraft (jet ski), receiving a direct high-pressure water jet impact to the perineal region, resulting in visible intense bleeding and pain.

During her initial evaluation, she presented with a vaginal tear involving the posterior wall, the perineal body, the anterior rectal wall, and the posterior rectal wall.

She underwent surgical debridement and repair of the vaginal wall to control bleeding. She was then transferred to a tertiary care center. Upon arrival at the hospital, 24 hours after the perineal trauma, she was evaluated by the Colorectal and Robotic Surgery Team of Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal. She was found to be tachycardic, tachypneic, awake, restless, conscious, with severe pain rated 10/10 (on the Numerical Rating Scale), no facial abnormalities, no chest abnormalities, abdomen with pain on moderate and deep palpation without signs of peritoneal irritation, but with intense and painful distension in the lower abdomen, and bowel sounds present. In the perineum, there was a hematoma extending throughout the entire perineal area with significant edema; the vagina showed suture marks from an attempted repair at the accident site. Further digital or manual evaluation was omitted due to the risk of aggravating the injury.

An MRI of the abdominal and pelvic region was requested, revealing:

- Grade III injury (complete rupture) of the left levator ani muscle from the midline, as well as of the internal and external anal sphincter muscles, transverse perineal (superficial and deep), perineal body, and anococcygeal ligament.
- Grade I injury (distension without rupture of muscle fibers) of the bulbospongiosus muscle, both internal obturators, and iliopsoas muscles.
- Findings consistent with rectal and sigmoid tear extending approximately 10 cm proximally.
- Findings suggestive of a tear throughout the entire length of the vaginal canal.
- Image suggestive of a metallic foreign body located in the subcutaneous cellular tissue adjacent to the left of the midline, near the pubic symphysis.
- Generalized soft tissue edema in the perineal region.
- The bladder shows distension with thin walls and no evidence of intraluminal filling defects. The visible portion of the urethra maintains normal anatomical characteristics.

Urology was consulted to rule out any urethral injury and to place a Foley catheter under ureteroscopy. Based on these findings, the decision was made to proceed with surgical washout and debridement, as well as possible primary repair and diverting colostomy.

Once the Foley catheter was placed by urology in the operating room under general anesthesia, in the lithotomy position, external surgical debridement was performed, and the vagina was explored (Fig. 1). It showed a continuous suture from the proximal apex to the perineal region. There were no defects in the closure and no communication with the

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Figure 1. A) Vagina with continuous suture from the proximal apex to the perineal region. B) Necrotic and edematized fatty tissue, posterior rectal wall with loss of continuity from the anal margin up to approximately 12 cm.

perineal body or rectal mucosa. The perineal body showed suture material, with no observed communication between the perineal body and rectum. In the posterior sector, there was abundant drainage of turbid fluid, necrotic and edematous fatty tissue; the posterior rectal wall showed loss of continuity from the anal margin to approximately 12 cm (Fig. 1). There was also loss of continuity of the internal and external anal sphincter muscles in the posterior sector, with ruptured muscle fibers of the left levator ani visible. Additionally, there was loss of continuity of skin and subcutaneous tissue in the posterior midline, as well as loss of the superficial and deep post-anal spaces. The coccyx was exposed.

Surgical scrubbing and debridement of necrotic tissue are performed. After evaluating the anatomy and once the surgical cleansing is completed, it is decided to begin repair of the anterior rectal wall, which is minimal and is closed with continuous sutures. Subsequently, the posterior apex of the rectal rupture is identified, and closure is performed up to the anal margin.

Next, the ends of the external anal sphincter are identified and closed by overlapping with interrupted sutures. Although visualization of muscular structures is not entirely clear, it is decided to perform repair of what could be the internal anal sphincter. The deep and superficial post-anal spaces are deliberately left open for drainage.

Once the perineal stage is completed, the patient is placed in the supine position, and the abdominal stage is initiated with the laparoscopy team. An umbilical incision is made, and under direct vision, the abdominal cavity is entered with a 12 mm trocar, establishing pneumoperitoneum. A 12 mm trocar is placed in the right lower quadrant 2 cm from the iliac crest, another 5 mm trocar is placed in the midclavicular line 2 cm below the costal margin, and a fourth trocar is placed at the previously marked site for colostomy in the left paramedian line at the level of the umbilical scar.

Diagnostic laparoscopy is performed without identifying lesions; the peritoneal reflection shows no bulging or hematomas, only intense edema of pelvic tissues and free fluid with inflammatory response. The sigmoid colon is identified, grasped with an intestinal clamp, and the intra-abdominal colostomy site is marked. The sigmoid colon is freed from the fascia of Toldt, and an external skin incision is started at the colostomy site without removing the 5 mm trocar. Dissection is carried out by planes down to the abdominal cavity, and the sigmoid colon is exteriorized. Pneumoperitoneum is re-established, and the sigmoid colon is checked to ensure it is not twisted or ischemic. Trocars are removed, and hemostasis is verified. The intra-abdominal stage is concluded.

Subsequently, surgical wounds are closed by layers up to the skin, and maturation of the colostomy is begun with subcutaneous Vicryl sutures; maturation is completed, and the surgical procedure is finished.

The patient is transferred to intermediate care for postoperative management, pain control, kept on absolute bed rest, with antithrombotic measures and broad-spectrum antibiotics.

On the third postoperative day, surgical lavage was required but no additional surgical procedure was needed. Diet is started once gas is passed through the colostomy, and later progressed to a soft diet.

Discharge is decided at 14 days postoperatively with a functional colostomy. Oral diet, urination via Foley catheter as per urology service indication. The patient showed no signs of systemic inflammatory response, with normal laboratory tests and completed antibiotic course.

The evolution at home has been satisfactory, with continued outpatient management and no hospital readmissions.

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III. RESULTS

Anorectal manometry is performed at 6 months post-trauma and post-surgery with the following results:

- Resting pressure of the internal anal sphincter: 28.47 mmHg (Normal: 40-80 mmHg)
- Phasic pressure of the external anal sphincter: 42.52 mmHg (Normal: 80-160 mmHg)
- Anal pressure during defecation maneuver: 41.15 mmHg
- Sensitivity to distension: 60 cc
- Rectal capacity: 100 cc

Based on the obtained results, anorectal rehabilitation is initiated for 8 sessions. Once the rehabilitation is completed, anorectal manometry is repeated with the following results:

- Resting pressure of the internal anal sphincter: 38.47 mmHg
- Phasic pressure of the external anal sphincter: 96.87 mmHg
- Anal pressure during defecation maneuver: 10.0 mmHg
- Sensitivity to distension: 10 cc
- Rectal capacity: 160 cc

Pelvic magnetic resonance imaging is repeated, reporting: grade I injury to the gluteus medius, tensor fasciae latae, and iliopsoas muscles bilaterally, inflammatory changes at the level of the bilateral hip joint cartilage, bladder without lesions.

With these results, it is decided to perform laparoscopic colostomy closure, informing the patient of the risk of anal incontinence due to the type of trauma despite the manometric results. The laparoscopic procedure is initiated

the colostomy. The site for proximal colon transection is identified, and the anvil of the circular stapler is placed. The proximal colon with the anvil is introduced, and a 29 mm circular stapler (Ethicon) is inserted transanally up to the rectal stump. The proximal colon is positioned onto the rectal stump, and a colorectal anastomosis is performed using the double-stapled surgical technique. An air leak test is performed, which is negative, and the surgical procedure is concluded. No drain is placed, hemostasis is verified, trocars are removed under direct vision, and the laparoscopic ports are subsequently closed in layers up to the skin (Fig. 2).

The postoperative evolution is satisfactory, with adequate pain control (NRS 2/10), no nausea, no vomiting, passing gas, Foley catheter removed on the first postoperative day, liquid diet started on the third day with diet progression on the fourth day, and discharge home on the fifth postoperative day, tolerating oral diet, afebrile, without pain, having bowel movements per rectum, passing gas, not using diapers. Fecal continence is evaluated and scores 0 points on the Wexner scale, with follow-up in the outpatient clinic and maintaining 0 points on the Wexner scale.

As the only postoperative complication, she presented urinary retention on the second day after colostomy closure, requiring reinsertion of a Foley catheter, which was removed after 2 weeks.

After treatment, the patient has no anorectal sequelae, with complete continence to gas, solid and liquid stool, no urgency or rectal tenesmus, and quality of life practically at 100%. She is currently under treatment and evaluation for the bladder

Figure 2. A) Closure of the laparoscopic ports by layers up to the skin.

with dissection of the sigmoid colon up to the rectosigmoid junction. An Echelon Power stapler (Ethicon) is introduced, and stapler firing is performed requiring only one cartridge. Subsequently, the descending colon and remaining sigmoid are fully mobilized without needing to mobilize the splenic flexure.

Once the colon segment is fully mobilized laparoscopically, the procedure continues extracorporeally with dismantling of

complication, without it causing disabling impact on her daily life.

IV. DISCUSSION

Anorectal trauma represents an uncommon entity within the spectrum of abdominal and pelvic traumatic injuries, accounting for approximately 1% to 3% of colorectal traumas. Nevertheless, it is associated with high morbidity

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due to the anatomical complexity of the perineal region, the potential for fecal contamination, and the frequent involvement of adjacent structures such as the genitourinary tract, vagina, and pelvic floor muscles.

These characteristics mean that its management remains a subject of debate, particularly regarding the indication for fecal diversion, the use of pre-sacral drainage, and primary repair of extraperitoneal injuries.

The mechanism of injury described in this case corresponds to high-pressure water jet trauma, a relatively uncommon form of perineal injury that has been mainly reported in accidents associated with personal watercraft (jet skis). The hydraulic energy generated by these devices can cause rapid distension of the anal canal and distal rectum, resulting in extensive tears of the rectum, vagina, and perineal muscular structures.

In such cases, the magnitude of the injury may be disproportionate to the initial external findings, necessitating a thorough diagnostic evaluation.

The initial assessment of these patients should aim not only to identify rectal injuries but also to rule out involvement of neighboring structures, particularly the urinary tract and genital apparatus.

In the presented case, magnetic resonance imaging allowed for a more precise definition of the extent of pelvic floor muscle damage and the sphincter complex, as well as the length of the rectosigmoid tear. Although computed tomography is usually the study of choice in the acute trauma setting, magnetic resonance imaging can provide superior characterization of perineal muscular and ligamentous injuries.

From a therapeutic perspective, the management of rectal trauma has evolved considerably in recent decades.

Multiple studies have questioned the utility of pre-sacral drainage and distal rectal irrigation, which have not demonstrated benefits in reducing infectious complications. Currently, there is consensus that treatment should be individualized according to the location of the injury (intra-peritoneal or extra-peritoneal), the degree of tissue destruction, and the patient's physiological status.

In the present case, the patient had a complex injury characterized by an extensive tear of the posterior rectal wall, involvement of the sphincter complex, and destruction of the perineal body, in addition to a previously repaired vaginal injury. Given this scenario, a combined perineal and abdominal surgical approach was chosen. The perineal stage allowed for adequate surgical lavage and debridement of devitalized tissue, which constitutes a fundamental principle in the management of contaminated perineal wounds. Subsequently, primary repair of the rectal wall and reconstruction of the external anal sphincter using an overlapping technique were performed.

Primary repair of the sphincter complex in the context of acute trauma remains controversial. Some authors suggest deferring reconstruction in cases of extensive destruction due

to the difficulty in identifying anatomical planes and the risk of suboptimal functional outcomes. Nevertheless, in injuries where muscular planes can be identified, early repair may help preserve sphincter function and reduce the need for secondary reconstructive procedures, such as dynamic graciloplasty or sacral nerve stimulation.

The creation of a diverting colostomy remains a widely accepted strategy in patients with complex extraperitoneal injuries, sphincter apparatus involvement, or extensive perineal wounds. Diversion reduces local bacterial load, facilitates perineal wound management, and decreases the risk of pelvic septic complications.

Pelvic floor rehabilitation plays a crucial role in the functional recovery of these patients, as it improves muscle strength, defecatory coordination, and rectal sensitivity. The results obtained in this case allowed consideration of colostomy closure with an acceptable functional risk.

Closure of the diversion was performed via a laparoscopic approach with colorectal anastomosis using the double-stapled technique, a procedure that has proven to be safe and effective in selected patients.

Overall, this case illustrates that the successful management of complex anorectal trauma requires an individualized and multidisciplinary approach that includes thorough diagnostic evaluation, timely surgical debridement, selective repair of injured structures, protective fecal diversion, and functional rehabilitation.

V. CONCLUSION

High-pressure water jet anorectal trauma is a rare injury that can cause extensive damage to the rectum, the sphincter complex, and the pelvic floor structures. Its management requires a comprehensive evaluation and an individualized surgical approach.

In this case, treatment through debridement, selective repair of the injured structures, and diverting colostomy allowed adequate control of contamination and promoted healing. Subsequently, anorectal rehabilitation contributed to functional recovery, enabling safe closure of the colostomy. Despite the severity of the initial injury, timely and multidisciplinary management can achieve satisfactory functional outcomes and preserve anal continence.

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